

Study of Sepsis and its Markers in Renal Failure Patients on Hemodialysis**Manish Gautam¹, Binod Kumar²**¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Lord Buddha Koshi Medical College and Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, India²Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Shri Ramkrishna Institute of Medical Sciences and Sanaka Hospital, Durgapur, West Bengal, India

Received: 10-06-2023 / Revised 16-07-2023 / Accepted 29-07-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Binod Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** The present study was conducted to study the presence of bacteremia, markers of sepsis and Inflammation in renal failure patients on hemodialysis, along with correlation of hematological abnormalities with sepsis in such patients.**Material & Methods:** The present study was conducted at department of General medicine for one year and total of 100 patients of both sexes who were diagnosed as case of renal failure which include both acute kidney injury (AKI) and CKD on basis of clinical history, examination, biochemical markers and were advised for hemodialysis were included in the study.**Results:** In our study among 100 patients of renal failure on hemodialysis the mean age in our study was 44.76±14.46 years with 65 male patients. Out of 100 patients 20 (20%) had positive blood and catheter tip culture and 80 (80%) of patients had negative blood and catheter tip culture. Out of 20 patients with sepsis 4 (20%) were in the age group between 15–25 years, 4 (20%) were in the age group between 26–35 years, 3 (15%) were in the age group 36–45 years and 9 (45%) were above 45 years of age. All 20 (100%) patients had episode of fever with chills and rigor, 9 (45%) patients had redness and pain at hemodialysis catheter site, 6 patients (30%) were confused, disoriented or comatose and 4 (20%) patients had hypotension. Among 20 patients of renal failure with sepsis, none had TLC less than 4.8/cumm (leucopenia), 5 (25%) patients had count between 4.8–10.8/cumm and 15 (75%) patients had TLC more than 10.8/cumm.**Conclusion:** Patients requiring hemodialysis, who are having non modifiable risk factors like age, sex other risk factors for infection should be controlled to reduce incidence of infection.**Keywords:** Sepsis, Chronic kidney disease, Hemodialysis, Blood stream infectionThis is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Sepsis is a life-threatening systemic inflammatory response to an infection that might result in organ injury, shock, or death. [1,2] In the United States, sepsis ranks as the 10th leading cause of death, and it accounts for 10% of all ICU admissions. [3] Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is fast emerging as a major public health problem in the 21st century. The National Kidney Foundation Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative guidelines defined CKD as kidney damage or a glomerular filtration rate of less than 60 ml/min per 1.73 m² for at least 3 months. [4] The CKD population is predisposed to adverse infectious events because of overwhelming uremia, which is associated with alterations in primary host defense mechanisms and increases the risk of bacterial infections and three most commonly seen infectious complications are urinary tract infections (UTI), pneumonia, and sepsis. [5] Sepsis-associated acute kidney injury (S-

AKI) is a common complication in hospitalized and critically ill patients, which increases the risk of developing chronic comorbidities and is associated with extremely high mortality. AKI of any origin is associated with higher risk of developing sepsis. [6] The diagnosis of AKI is currently based on an increase serum creatinine concentration and/or a decrease in urine output. [7,8] As in other forms of AKI, serum creatinine can be an insensitive indicator of kidney injury, and oliguria can be nonspecific in S-AKI. One of the most serious and life-threatening infections in dialysis patients is septicemia. The sepsis is complicated by the use of immunosuppressive drugs to treat and control underlying diseases and exacerbated by nutritional deficiencies, the dialysis procedure and the disruption of cutaneous or mucosal barriers to infection. [9] It accounts for over three fourths of deaths caused by infections. [10] The annual percentage of mortality secondary to sepsis is

approximately 100 to 300 fold higher in dialysis patients. [11] Gram-negative bacteria were previously the most common cause of sepsis, in the last decade, gram-positive bacteria, most commonly staphylococci cause more than 50% of cases of sepsis. [12] Uremia often results in immune deficiency. ¹³ Malnourishment and older age may interact with uremia to impair the immune system. Risk may also vary according to the presence of comorbid conditions such as diabetes mellitus (DM) and disruptions of dermal barriers to gain access for dialysis. [14,15] In peritoneal dialysis (PD), infection may occur through either the catheter entrance through the skin or the peritoneal cavity. [13] In hemodialysis (HD) patients, infection may occur from the need for intravascular catheters to perform dialysis. [13] Infection may also depend on the type of vascular access used to conduct HD, reuse practices, and membrane selection. [16] Those with temporary catheters had been shown to have a 50% higher risk of septicemia than patients with a native fistula. Catheter-related bloodstream infection (CRBSI also called catheter-related sepsis) is defined as the presence of bacteraemia originating from a central intravenous catheter. It is one of the most frequent and lethal complications of central venous catheterization. Almost all HD catheters had biofilm formation on their surfaces and this serves as a good reservoir for microorganisms. [17]

The present study was conducted to study the presence of bacteremia, markers of sepsis and Inflammation in renal failure patients on hemodialysis, along with correlation of hematological abnormalities with sepsis in such patients.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted at department of General medicine Lord Buddha Koshi Medical College and Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, India for 1 years and total of 100 patients of both sexes who were diagnosed as case of renal failure which include both acute kidney injury (AKI) and CKD on basis of clinical history, examination, biochemical markers and were advised for hemodialysis were included in the study. The criteria used for AKI in the study was risk, injury, failure, loss of kidney function, and end-stage kidney disease (RIFLE) criteria. [18] The kidney disease outcomes quality initiative (KDOQI) defines CKD as either kidney damage or a decreased glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of less than 60 ml/min/1.73 m² for 3 or more months. [19] Criteria for the systemic inflammatory response syndrome, adapted from the American college of chest physicians/society of critical care medicine consensus conference. [20]

Inclusion Criteria:

Patients of renal failure with newly inserted hemodialysis catheter subclavian venous catheter, internal jugular venous catheter or femoral catheter who developed systemic signs and symptom of sepsis e.g. fever, chills and rigor, tachycardia, tachypnea, hypotension, confusion, disorientation, and agitation after hemodialysis catheter insertion and hemodialysis and patients with local swelling, redness, pain or pus discharge at the site of hemodialysis catheter.

Exclusion Criteria;

Those patients who had renal failure due to septicemia or post-operative renal failure, had history of hemodialysis in past, had known source of infection e.g. diabetic foot, pyelonephritis, bedsore, or had A-V fistula.

After recruiting patient for study, clinical history and relevant blood and radiological investigation (hemoglobin, total leucocyte count (TLC), differential leucocyte count (DLC), and platelet count), renal function test (RFT) (serum creatinine, blood urea, and serum electrolyte), serum phosphorus, C-reactive protein, liver function test (LFT) (serum bilirubin, serum total protein, serum albumin, alkaline phosphatase), thyroid function test – TFT (T₃, T₄, and thyroid stimulating hormone-TSH), urine routine and microscopy, urine culture and sensitivity, blood culture, central line catheter tip culture sensitivity, chest X-ray (CXR) P/A view, ultrasonography (USG) abdomen and kidney, ureter and bladder (KUB) were performed. Leukocyte count and blood culture were done prior to catheter insertion and a single sample was collected from the peripheral vein before insertion of the catheter to rule out any existing bacteremia. If positive, the patient was excluded from the study. Secondly, after 72 hours of the insertion, two 5 ml samples of blood were collected, one from the peripheral vein and the other from the catheters; the latter being collected after at least 12 hours of hemodialysis.

In the laboratory, subcultures were done from Hartley's broth onto blood agar (BA) and MacConkey medium after overnight incubation at 37 °C and also on the 2nd, 4th and 7th days and were then discarded, if negative. [21] Aseptically collected mid-stream urine sample in sterile bottle containing boric acid was transported to microbiology laboratory. Bacterial culture was performed by streaking 0.002 ml of mid-stream collected urine with a standard calibrated loop on MacConkey agar and 5% sheep blood agar plates which was incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours, under aerobic conditions and the colonies was counted by a colony counter. Sample that yielded pure bacterial growth of $\geq 10^5$ cfu/ml was regarded as significant bacteriuria. Counts between 10⁴ and 10⁵ cfu/ml repeated while counts $\leq 10^4$ cfu/ml

considered as negative. [22] Catheter tip was collected only from patients who had their catheters removed on completion of their HD sessions or in case they showed any signs of infection. It was cultured by Maki's standard semi quantitative method on blood agar and then put in trypticase soy broth (TSB).

Statistical Analysis

A colony count of ≥ 15 was considered significant for cultures done by Maki's method. [21] If the same organisms grew from both peripheral and central venous catheter (CVC) blood cultures confirmation was done by the pour-plate quantitative method. [23] Association and correlation assessment were done by statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS).

Results

Table 1: Patients on hemodialysis with sepsis and gender distribution

Parameter	Renal failure patients on hemodialysis with symptoms of sepsis	
	N=100	%
Positive blood/catheter tip culture	20	20
Negative blood/catheter tip culture	80	80
Total	100	
Gender		
Male	65	65
Female	35	35

In our study among 100 patients of renal failure on hemodialysis the mean age in our study was 44.76 ± 14.46 years with 65 male patients. Out of 100 patients 20 (20%) had positive blood and catheter tip culture and 80 (80%) of patients had negative blood and catheter tip culture.

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to age groups, symptoms and TLC

Age groups	N%
15-25 years	4 (20)
26-35 years	4 (20)
36-45 years	3 (15)
>45 years	9 (45)
Symptoms	
Fever with chills and rigor	20 (100)
Redness and Pain at hemodialysis catheter site	9 (45)
Confused, Disoriented or comatose	6 (30)
Hypotension	4 (20)
TLC	
Less than 4.8/cumm (leucopenia),	0
Between 4.8–10.8/cumm	5 (25)
More than 10.8/cumm	15 (75)

Out of 20 patients with sepsis 4 (20%) were in the age group between 15–25 years, 4 (20%) were in the age group between 26–35 years, 3 (15%) were in the age group 36–45 years and 9 (45%) were above 45 years of age. All 20 (100%) patients had episode of fever with chills and rigor, 9 (45%) patients had redness and pain at hemodialysis

catheter site, 6 patients (30%) were confused, disoriented or comatose and 4 (20%) patients had hypotension. Among 20 patients of renal failure with sepsis, none had TLC less than 4.8/cumm (leucopenia), 5 (25%) patients had count between 4.8–10.8/cumm and 15 (75%) patients had TLC more than 10.8/cumm.

Table 3: Bacteria found on patients with sepsis

Type of bacteria	Renal failure patients on hemodialysis with sepsis	
	N=20	%
S. aureus	16	80
E. coli	2	10
Acinetobacter	1	5
Candida	1	5
Total	20	100

16 (80%) patients' blood culture was positive for S. aureus, and E. coli found in blood culture 2 (10%) patient, Acinetobacter in 1 (5%) patient and Candida in 1 (5%) patient.

Table 4: Most common catheter site associated with infection

Site of hemodialysis catheter	Renal failure patients on hemodialysis with sepsis	
	N=20	%
Internal jugular venous catheter	5	25
Femoral catheter	14	70
Subclavian catheter	1	5
Total	20	100

Among 20 patients of renal failure on hemodialysis with sepsis 5 (25%) patients had internal jugular line for hemodialysis, 1 (5%) had subclavian line and 14 (70%) had femoral line for hemodialysis.

Table 5: Distribution of patients according to catheter duration and serum phosphate and albumin levels

Catheter duration	N%
7-14 days	3 (15)
14-21 days	3 (15)
>21 days	14 (70)
Serum phosphate levels	
Less than 3.5 mg/dl	0
Between 3.5–5.5 mg/dl	4 (20)
>5.5 mg/dl	16 (80)
Serum albumin levels	
Less than 3.4 gm/dl	12 (60)
More than 3.4 gm/dl	8 (40)

Catheter duration of 7-14 days was found in 3 (15%), 3 (15%) patients had central line between 14–21 days, and 14 (70%) patients had central line >21 days. 15 patients of renal failure on hemodialysis with sepsis none had serum phosphate level less than 3.5 mg/dl, 4 (20%) had serum phosphorus level between 3.5–5.5 mg/dl and 16 (80%) patients had serum phosphorus level >5.5 mg/dl. Albumin level less than 3.4 gm/dl was found in 12 (60) patients, 8 (40%) had serum albumin level more than 3.4 gm/dl.

Discussion

Sepsis-associated acute kidney injury (S-AKI) is a common complication in hospitalized and critically ill patients, which increases the risk of developing chronic comorbidities and is associated with extremely high mortality. [24-26] As individual syndromes, sepsis and acute kidney injury (AKI) render the host susceptible to each other. Although sepsis is the most common contributing factor for developing AKI, AKI of any origin is associated with higher risk of developing sepsis. Sepsis has a complex and unique pathophysiology, which makes S-AKI a distinct syndrome from any other phenotype of AKI. [27]

Out of 20 patients with sepsis 4 (20%) were in the age group between 15–25 years, 4 (20%) were in the age group between 26–35 years, 3 (15%) were in the age group 36–45 years and 9 (45%) were above 45 years of age. All 20 (100%) patients had episode of fever with chills and rigor, 9 (45%) patients had redness and pain at hemodialysis catheter site, 6 patients (30%) were confused, disoriented or comatose and 4 (20%) patients had hypotension. We noted the incidence of sepsis was more in patients of age group greater than 45 years

of age. Longitudinal cohort study conducted by Powe et al showed that sepsis was more common in older age group. [28] In 2013 a study conducted by Gupta in 45 patients of CKD showed that the prevalence of CRBSI was 17.78% in patients above 65 years of age. [29] So, our study conforms with other studies, who had shown that advanced age is risk factor for CRBSI. Robinson et al found that fever was the most consistent symptom at onset of CRBSI (28 of 32 cases). [30] Kairaitis et al conducted a study of 105 haemodialysis catheters in 52 patients in order to identify patient outcomes and to analyse the effect of patient and catheter factors on the incidence of infectious complications, they found that exit-site infection was the cause for removal in 8% and most common clinical symptom was fever. [31]

Among 20 patients of renal failure with sepsis, none had TLC less than 4.8/cumm (leucopenia), 5 (25%) patients had count between 4.8–10.8/cumm and 15 (75%) patients had TLC more than 10.8/cumm. A study conducted by Gupta on 45 CKD patient on haemodialysis, catheter related infections were correlated with TLC. [29] 16 (80%) patients' blood culture was positive for *S. aureus*, and *E. coli* found in blood culture 2 (10%) patient, *Acinetobacter* in 1 (5%) patient and *Candida* in 1 (5%) patient. Nagarika et al in 2006-2007 conducted a study in 210 patients and found that bacteremia occurred in 17 (47.22%) patients with femoral catheter, 8 (22.22%) patients with subclavian catheter and 11 (30.55%) patients with jugular hemodialysis catheter. [32] Among 20 patients of renal failure on hemodialysis with sepsis 5 (25%) patients had internal jugular line for hemodialysis, 1 (5%) had subclavian line and 14 (70%) had femoral line for hemodialysis. Oliver et

al had shown that incidence of bacteremia was 5.4% after three weeks of placement in internal jugular vein and 10.7% after one week in femoral vein. [33]

Catheter duration of 7-14 days was found in 3 (15%), 3 (15%) patients had central line between 14–21 days, and 14 (70%) patients had central line >21 days. 15 patients of renal failure on hemodialysis with sepsis none had serum phosphate level less than 3.5 mg/dl, 4 (20%) had serum phosphorus level between 3.5–5.5 mg/dl and 16 (80%) patients had serum phosphorus level >5.5 mg/dl. Albumin level less than 3.4 gm/dl was found in 12 (60) patients, 8 (40%) had serum albumin level more than 3.4 gm/dl. study conducted by Plantinga had shown high phosphorus level was associated with infection in dialysis patients which supports our finding too. [34] We noted hypoalbuminemia is contributing to increased risk of catheter related infection matches with studies of Powe et al. [28] He suggested hypoalbuminemia was common in catheter related blood stream infection.

Conclusion

Incidence of renal failure requiring hemodialysis has increased and accordingly use of vascular access to deliver haemodialysis therapy has increased. The patient requiring haemodialysis are prone to infections because of risk factors like advanced age, male sex, diabetes, anemia, hypoalbuminemia, hyperphosphatemia and prolonged duration of hemodialysis. The site of vascular access is an important risk factor for development of sepsis. GPC (*S. aureus*) is the commonest cause of sepsis.

References

1. Levy MM, Fink MP, Marshall JC, Abraham E, Angus D, Cook D, Cohen J, Opal SM, Vincent JL, Ramsay G, International Sepsis Definitions Conference. 2001 sccm/esicm/accp/ats/sis international sepsis definitions conference. Intensive care medicine. 2003 Apr;29:530-8.
2. Mansur A, Mulwande E, Steinau M, Bergmann I, Frederik Popov A, Ghadimi M, Beissbarth T, Bauer M, Hinz J. Chronic kidney disease is associated with a higher 90-day mortality than other chronic medical conditions in patients with sepsis. Scientific reports. 2015 May 21;5(1):10539.
3. Bou Chebl R, Tamim H, Abou Dagher G, Sadat M, Ghamdi G, Itani A, Saeedi A, Arabi YM. Sepsis in end-stage renal disease patients: are they at an increased risk of mortality?. Annals of Medicine. 2021 Jan 1;53(1):1737-43.
4. Levey AS, Coresh J, Bolton K, Culleton B, Harvey KS, Ikizler TA, Johnson CA, Kausz A, Kimmel PL, Kusek J, Levin A. K/DOQI clinical practice guidelines for chronic kidney disease: evaluation, classification, and stratification. American Journal of Kidney Diseases. 2002;39.
5. Smith PS. Management of end-stage renal disease in children. Annals of Pharmacotherapy. 1998 Sep;32(9):929-39.
6. Peerapornratana S, Manrique-Caballero CL, Gómez H, Kellum JA. Acute kidney injury from sepsis: current concepts, epidemiology, pathophysiology, prevention and treatment. Kidney international. 2019 Nov 1;96(5):1083-99.
7. Bellomo R, Ronco C, Kellum JA, Mehta RL, Palevsky P. Acute renal failure—definition, outcome measures, animal models, fluid therapy and information technology needs: the Second International Consensus Conference of the Acute Dialysis Quality Initiative (ADQI) Group. Critical care. 2004 Aug;8(4):1-9.
8. Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) Acute Kidney Injury Work Group. KDIGO clinical practice guideline for acute kidney injury. Kidney Int Suppl. 2012;2:1–138.
9. Kessler M, Hoen B, Mayeux D, Hestin D, Fontenaille C. Bacteremia in patients on chronic hemodialysis. Nephron. 1993;64(1):95-100.
10. U.S. Renal Data System: USRDS 1997 Annual Data Report. National Institutes of Health, NIDDK, Bethesda, April, 1997
11. Sarnak MJ, Jaber BL. Mortality caused by sepsis in patients with end-stage renal disease compared with the general population. Kidney international. 2000 Oct 1;58(4):1758-64.
12. Hirasawa H, Oda SH, Nakamura M. Blood glucose control in patients with severe sepsis and septic shock. World J Gastroenterol. 2000; 15(33):4132-6
13. Powe NR, Jaar B, Furth SL, Hermann J, Briggs W. Septicemia in dialysis patients: incidence, risk factors, and prognosis. Kidney international. 1999 Mar 1;55(3):1081-90.
14. Carton JA, Maradona JA, Nuno FJ, Fernandez-Alvarez R, Perez-Gonzalez F, Asensi V. Diabetes mellitus and bacteraemia: a comparative study between diabetic and non-diabetic patients. The European journal of medicine. 1992 Sep 1;1(5):281-7.
15. Khan IH, Catto GR. Long-term complications of dialysis: infection. Kidney International Supplement. 1993 Jun 2(41).
16. Feldman HI, Kinosian M, Bilker WB, Simmons C, Holmes JH, Pauly MV, Escarc JJ. Effect of dialyzer reuse on survival of patients treated with hemodialysis. JAMA. 1996 Aug 28;276(8):620-5.
17. Fletcher SJ, Bodenham AR. Catheter-related sepsis: an overview-Part 2. British Journal of Intensive Care. 1999;9:74-81.

18. Biesen WV, Vanholder R, Lameire N. Defining Acute Renal Failure: RIFLE and Beyond. *CJASN*. 2006;1(6):1314-9.
19. National Kidney Foundation: K/DOQI clinical practice guidelines for chronic kidney disease: Definition, identification, and prediction of CKD progression *Kidney International Supplements*. 2013; 3:63-72.
20. American College of Chest Physicians/Society of Critical Care Medicine Consensus Conference. Definitions for sepsis and organ failure and guidelines for the use of innovative therapies in sepsis. *Crit Care Med*. 1992; 20:864-74.
21. Maki DG, Weise CE, Sarafin HW. A semi-quantitative culture method for identifying intravenous catheter related infection. *N Eng J Med*. 1997;296(23):1305-9.
22. Chukwu BF, Okafor HU, Ikefuna AN. Asymptomatic bacteriuria in children with sickle cell anemia at The University of Nigeria teaching hospital, Enugu, South East, Nigeria. *Italian Journal of pediatrics*. 2011 Dec;37(1):1-5.
23. Quilici N, Audibert G, Conroy MC, Bollaert PE, Guillemin F, Welfringer P, Garric J, Weber M, Laxenaire MC. Differential quantitative blood cultures in the diagnosis of catheter-related sepsis in intensive care units. *Clinical infectious diseases*. 1997 Nov 1;25(5):1066-70.
24. Uchino S. Beginning and Ending Supportive Therapy for the Kidney (BEST Kidney) Investigators. Acute renal failure in critically ill patients: a multinational, multicenter study. *JAMA*. 2005; 294:813-8.
25. Bagshaw SM, Uchino S, Bellomo R, Morimatsu H, Morgera S, Schetz M, Tan I, Bouman C, Macedo E, Gibney N, Tolwani A. Septic acute kidney injury in critically ill patients: clinical characteristics and outcomes. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*. 2007 May 1;2(3):431-9.
26. Bouchard J, Acharya A, Cerda J, Maccariello ER, Madarasu RC, Tolwani AJ, Liang X, Fu P, Liu ZH, Mehta RL. A prospective international multicenter study of AKI in the intensive care unit. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*. 2015 Aug 7;10(8):1324-31.
27. Mehta RL, Bouchard J, Soroko SB, Ikizler TA, Paganini EP, Chertow GM, Himmelfarb J, Program to Improve Care in Acute Renal Disease (PICARD) Study Group. Sepsis as a cause and consequence of acute kidney injury: Program to Improve Care in Acute Renal Disease. *Intensive care medicine*. 2011 Feb;37: 241-8.
28. Powe NR, Jaar B, Furth SL, Hermann J, Briggs W. Septicemia in dialysis patients: incidence, risk factors, and prognosis. *Kidney international*. 1999 Mar 1;55(3):1081-90.
29. Punit G, Khunte P, Dubey P, Gupta GB. Catheter Related Infection In Geriatric Population On Hemodialysis, A Study From Central India. *Rep Opinion*. 2014;6(5):24-6.
30. Robinson JL, Casey LM, Huynh HQ, Spady DW. Prospective cohort study of the outcome of and risk factors for intravascular catheter-related bloodstream infections in children with intestinal failure. *J Parenter Enteral Nutr*. 2014; 38(5):625-30.
31. Kairaitis LK, Gottlieb T. Outcome and complications of temporary haemodialysis catheters. *Nephrology, dialysis, transplantation: official publication of the European Dialysis and Transplant Association-European Renal Association*. 1999 Jul 1;14(7):1710-4.
32. Nagarik AP, Soni S, Barnela S, Gondane S, Kishan AG. Bacteremia Following Temporary Hemodialysis Catheter Insertion: A Prospective Study. *Indian Journal of Nephrology*. 2007 Jul 1;17(3).
33. Oliver MJ, Callery SM, Thorpe KE, Schwab SJ, Churchill DN. Risk of bacteremia from temporary hemodialysis catheters by site of insertion and duration of use: a prospective study. *Kidney international*. 2000 Dec 1;58(6): 2543-5.
34. Plevkova J. Systemic inflammatory response syndrome. *JFMED*. 2011;122-4.